

Welcome to the 9th volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

Dear Reader, we wish you a great day and encourage you to read our newsletter. In this volume we present to you a part of the progress made within EU-HIP in Italy and Norway, we invite you to our last Symposium and introduce you to SHAIPEP.

Let's dive into this volume!

Progress in Italy and Norway

During the scope of EU-HIP, countries have invested into the development of new IT solutions and upgrades of existing infrastructure with the aim to achieve interoperability with ATHINA. Since we are reaching the final weeks of our project, it is a great time to highlight some achievements reached within partner countries.

Highlight from Italy: PREMAL

PREMAL (Italian: Piattaforma Regionale Monitoraggio e ALerta) is a new national platform designed for the surveillance and alerting of infectious diseases in Italy. PREMAL supports real-time surveillance of communicable diseases and public health threats. It aggregates epidemiological data from regional health authorities and laboratories providing dashboards, alerting mechanisms, trend analysis and reporting functionalities to national authorities.

Under EU-HIP, PREMAL was significantly upgraded. Enhancements included improved data ingestion pipelines, API-based interoperability layers, harmonized metadata structures, enhanced analytics modules and secure data exchange capabilities. The development primarily focused on improving interoperability, cross-regional data exchange, data quality validation mechanisms and partial workflow automation for outbreak reporting. PREMAL aligns with European surveillance standards and WHO case definitions. Structured datasets follow harmonized epidemiological data models compatible with ECDC reporting schemas. Standard terminologies (ICD, SNOMED CT where applicable) and HL7 FHIR-based APIs were progressively adopted.

Progress in Italy

Progress in Norway

In Norway, the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) has served as the beneficiary in EU-HIP, with the Directorate of Health (NDH) acting as the affiliated entity. As a result, the activities carried out under EU-HIP have been implemented across these two organizations. NIPH is responsible for the areas related to Pathogens with High Pandemic Potential (PHPP) and antimicrobial resistance (AMR), while NDH has the overarching health-sector role for medical countermeasures (MCM) and chemical, biological, radiological & nuclear threats (CBRN). However, for MCM and CBRN domains multiple national actors share responsibilities and mandates.

NIPH has set a future target for a data-driven National system for infectious disease surveillance and has invested funds provided within the EU-HIP project to invest into multiple domains marked in the figure below with green stars. These activities represent key building blocks towards a more coherent and modernized national surveillance architecture and demonstrate how EU-HIP has enabled Norway to progress substantially in strengthening preparedness, improving data flows and aligning with European surveillance capabilities.

In this Newsletter we want to highlight one of many progresses made during our project by NIPH – the MSIS-laboratory database which forms an integral part of Norway's national surveillance system for infectious diseases.

MSIS is the legally mandated national registry for reporting and monitoring communicable diseases and is operated by the NIPH under the MSIS Regulation. While the core MSIS system collects clinical notifications and microbiological results, the MSIS-laboratory database provides a broader overview of national laboratory testing activity. This includes information on test volumes, locations, and the infectious agents being analyzed. These insights are essential for distinguishing between true changes in disease occurrence and fluctuations caused by varying testing activity. By enriching MSIS with granular information on laboratory practices, Norway achieves more accurate interpretation of surveillance signals, earlier detection of unusual developments, and better-informed public health responses. The system also supports statistics research, preparedness planning, and evaluation of preventive measures by offering a coherent picture of both disease burden and underlying testing patterns.

During the EU-HIP project, the MSIS-laboratory database underwent significant upgrades. The raw dataset was systematically standardized, and a new database containing fully cleaned and harmonized data was established. This work greatly improved the reliability and usability of national laboratory data and laid the foundation for more advanced analytical and surveillance functionality in the future. The figure below shows the component of the system developed during EUHIP, highlighted within the blue frame.

We invite you to the final EU-HIP Symposium

4th EU-HIP Symposium

March 24th to 26th 2026

Royal Library, Copenhagen, Denmark

The time has come to wrap-up our project with an in-person event which will take place in Copenhagen, Denmark from March 24th to 26th. During the three-day event we will have a chance to reflect on all the progress made in the past years. Work package leaders will report on the final results and deliverables which are either published or near the final form. All participating countries will have the chance to present their key achievements, fostering exchange of experiences and lessons learned, enabling better oversight of activities and future collaborations. Interactive workshops on standards and EHDS will open the floor for discussion among participants to find a common ground and give recommendations on how to achieve interoperability on all levels and within the ever-changing European landscape of health data exchange.

Introducing: SHAIPEd

Supporting Health Data Access Bodies to establish AI pathways enabling Deployment of AI as medical device tools. Empowering AI in Healthcare through Enhanced Data Access. SHAIPEd supports the development of AI as a medical device by optimizing data pathways and enabling Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs) to strengthen the European Health Data Space.

SHAIPEd is a project funded by the EU's Digital Europe Program. It aims to create secure, efficient, and regulation-compliant pathways for the development and deployment of artificial intelligence (AI) as medical devices. By optimizing how Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs) collaborate across Europe, SHAIPEd leverages the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation and AI Act to improve patient outcomes, reduce time-to-market for AI medical devices, and strengthen the EU's leadership in digital healthcare innovation.

[Visit SHAIPEd](#)